

CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT WITH REFERENCE TO TWO WHEELER: A STUDY OF REWARI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

In developing country like India, where sizeable proportion of population comprises of middle class, and where 70% lives in rural areas, a two wheeler is considered to be the most suitable vehicle. Indian two wheeler industries are the largest in the world as far as volume of production and sales are concerned and there is stiff competition in the market. Therefore, two wheeler companies are using different mean of promotion, like personnel selling, exhibition and fair, newspaper paper advertisement, TV advertisement, Celebrity endorsement etc. This research paper is attempted to measure consumer perception towards celebrity endorsement. For this purpose a questionnaire is framed and distributed among the users' of two wheeler in Rewari District. Out of 250 distributed questionnaires 200 valid questionnaires were received and data were analysed with the help of frequency & chi square test. It is found that rural area respondents are highly motivated with celebrity endorsement & all respondents irrespective of age, gender & residential status are not in favor to pay high price and not able to remove the confusion of respondents.

Key Words: Celebrity Endorsement, Perception, Image & Value, Purchase Decision

Introduction:

The modern day market place is very attractive in terms of purchasing power but equally competitive. Marketing is essentially about identifying customer needs and responding to those changing needs with appropriate product offers. Basically, customer needs are the starting point for marketing activity. Marketing is basically an exchange process. It involves, understanding the customers interest and developing products to satisfy these needs. The next step is promotion of the products. Grabbing attention, informing people and making a specific place in the mind of the consumer is the actual challenge for the marketers. The market today has become very competitive and in order to survive, marketers have to develop innovative ideas which can impact the consumers.

Celebrity Endorsement in India:

Celebrity Endorsement in India started in the late 1980's. Whether it was a film actor or a television actor or a famous sports star, everyone started increasing into the new territory of product endorsement. Many stars were seen advocating some or the other producing during the 1980's and 1990's. It was this period, which saw the beginning of the advertisements of Lux soap, which over a period of time has managed to associate with the leading female actors of Bollywood. Today, after a period of almost 30 years, the entire celebrity endorsement market has changed. Today, it is a competitive market wherein the success of a particular celebrity will determine the number of products that he / she will endorse. In the year 2008, popular Bollywood actor Shah Rukh Khan topped the list of endorsing as many as 39 brands, Sachin Tendulkar, M.S Dhoni, Virat Kohli are topped in the list of celebrity endorsement.

Celebrity Endorsement:

A celebrity is a person of high credentials peoples such as Movie stars, Sports icons, TV personalities or popular entertainers. They have high attention grabbing power. A large segment of the audience can instantly recognize and identify with the famous person and the affection and goodwill associated with him/ her can be transferred to the products. A celebrity endorser is a celebrity who endorses the brand normally over the media. In other words, a celebrity endorser is an individual who is known to the public for his or her achievement in the areas other than that of the product class endorsed. Celebrities are people who enjoy public recognition by a large number of people and enjoy a high degree of public awareness.

Review of Literature:

Murugan Sakthivel M., (2014) in his study "*Perception of Women Consumer towards the purchase decision of two wheelers in India: A study with Reference to Metropolitan Cities*", reveals that the perception of women consumers towards the two wheeler purchase decision differ widely. The researcher finds that "region" effect is an in substantial factor in two wheeler users' evaluation. Other factors such as promotional schemes, Performance, utilitarian benefits, personal factors and value added benefits were perceived by women consumers in four cities as more important than regions. Thus the overall findings of the study provide

implications for marketers and manufacturers of women two wheelers, B.Krishan and Chandhini P. S, (2016) in his study “Customer perception toward celebrity endorsement” find that most of the customers are partly satisfied with celebrity endorsement. While going through the data analysis it is evident that consumers are indeed influenced by the celebrity endorsement during a purchase decision. The customers give more preference to quality of the product. They are give little consideration to the celebrity who endorse it. Celebrity endorsement is the only the means of promotion of the product, Rangrajan P. and Sathya R. (2014) in his study “A Study on Impact of celebrity endorsement on brand perception and buying behavior of consumer with reference to UDUMALPET TALUK” observed that 73% respondents influence to purchase a product and create a position affirmation in multiple endorsement of celebrity for a single brand has a high level of influence over consumer buying behavior, Kumar Vikas and Singh Bikramjit, (2015) in his study “Customer perception toward celebrity endorsement” find that attractiveness of a celebrity endorsing a particular product/brand strongly influence a customer perception and impact of product and brand are more positive on the customer buying decision compare to celebrity endorsement. So celebrities' professional accomplishments and expertise may serve as a logical connection with the products, and consequently make the endorsement more believable to consumers, Poonam Arora and G.S.Batra (2013), in their research paper “Customer perception about celebrity endorsement” revealed that company should invest on the advertisements according to the choices of respondents that is TV advertisement and Radio advertisement more impressive than other marketing communication channels. Strategy of the company should be according to age, gender and profession while taking the different celebrity in the advertisement and Saheed et al., (2014) in their research “Impact of celebrity and non celebrity advertisement on consumer perception” revealed that there is a positive relation of celebrity advertisement and non celebrity advertisement on consumer perception, but celebrity endorsement has greater impact on consumer perception than non celebrity advertisement because, the celebrity has already established a meaning outside the advertisement world. Celebrities have more credibility in conveying a meaningful message and admire them.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the effective medium of celebrity endorsement.
- ✓ To study the perception of consumer about celebrity endorsement with reference to two wheeler.

Hypothesis:

Ho1: There is no significance difference between the celebrity endorsement and non celebrity endorsement with reference to respondents demographic characteristic i.e. residential status, gender and age.

Ho2: Consumer perception about celebrity endorsement does not significantly influence by their demographic characteristic i.e. residential status, gender and age.

Research Methodology:

This study use Descriptive research design, it is descriptive because, researchers try to analysis the perception of respondents toward celebrity endorsement with reference to residential area, gender and age of the respondents in detail. Population of above 18 years of age of Rewari District constitute the universe of the study, only people having two wheeler and users of two wheeler constitute survey population. Individual who are using two-wheeler were sample unit for the study. 200 respondents were selected through purposive sampling method, out of 200, 100 respondents were male and 100 were female, out of 100 male and female respondents 50 respondents from rural and urban area from each category. For collecting primary data a questionnaire was designed and divides in to two parts. Part A belong to demographic characteristics, Part B belong to Medium of Advertisement and perception of respondents towards celebrity endorsement. The statement use to major the perception of respondents are as

Statements

SA A N D SD

- Celebrity endorsement increases my awareness of their endorsed two wheeler Brand
- Celebrity endorsement affects my selection of alternative brands during evaluation process
- Celebrity endorsement helps me to recall or remember their endorsed two wheeler brand during buying
- When I am confused about two wheeler product, I believe celebrity endorsement
- I am interested in two wheeler brand which use Celebrity endorsement
- I would buy a brand if my Favorite Celebrity is endorsing it
- Celebrity endorser’s image and value increase their endorsed
- Two wheeler product image and value
- I am willing to pay high price for two wheeler brand which endorsed by celebrity
- Celebrity endorsement is very effective in making my purchase decision about two wheeler.

Result:

Table 1: Best Media to Convey Celebrity Endorsement Advertisement

Media	Frequency	Percent
Television	116	58.0
Newspaper	27	13.5
Magazines	10	5.0

Radio	00	0.0
Internet	47	23.5
Total	200	100

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire Dec. 2017)

Table 1 revealed that most of the respondents (58%) indicate that television is the best medium of communication to convey the message with the help of celebrity, Internet comes at 2nd place, newspaper at 3rd place and magazines & radio are least popular medium of communication.

Table 2: More Effective Advertisement

Variables		Celebrity Endorsed Advertisement	Non Celebrity Advertisement	Chi Square Value	Result
Residential Status	Urban	79	21	.009<0.05	Sig.
	Rural	92	08		
	Total	171	29		
Gender	Male	82	18	.160>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	89	11		
	Total	171	29		
Age	18-25	59	05	.183>0.05	Not Sig.
	26-35	56	12		
	Above 35	56	12		
	Total	171	29		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire Dec. 2017)

Table 2 revealed that there is no significance difference among the respondents according to gender & age of the respondents they feel that both kind of advertisement i.e. celebrity and non celebrity are equally effective. But in case of residential status rural area respondents are in favor of celebrity advertisement i.e. celebrity advertisement are more effective than the non celebrity advertisement at 95% level of significance.

Table 3: Consumer Perception about Celebrity Endorsement with Reference to Residential Status

Statement	Residential Status	Aware	Not Aware	Chi-Square Value/P Value	Result
S1	Urban	92(46.0%)	08(4.0%)	.234>0.05	Not Sig.
	Rural	96(48.0%)	04(2.0%)		
	Total	188(94.0%)	12(6.0%)		
S2		Affect	Not Effect	.002<0.05	Sig.
	Urban	68(34.0%)	32(16.0%)		
	Rural	82(41.0%)	18(9.0%)		
	Total	150(75.0%)	50(25.0%)		
S3		Recall	Not Recall	.547>0.05	Not Sig.
	Urban	65(32.5%)	35(17.5%)		
	Rural	69(34.5%)	31(15.5%)		
	Total	134(67.0%)	66(33.0%)		
S4		Believe	Not Believe	.718>0.05	Not Sig.
	Urban	18(9.0%)	82(41.0%)		
	Rural	20(10.0%)	80(40.0%)		
	Total	38(19.0%)	162(81.0%)		
S5		Interested	Not Interested	.001<0.05	Sig.
	Urban	60(30.0%)	40(20.0%)		
	Rural	81(40.5%)	19(9.5%)		
	Total	141(70.5%)	59(29.5%)		
S6		Buy	Not Buy	.082>0.05	Not Sig.
	Urban	84(42.0%)	16(8.0%)		
	Rural	92(46.0%)	8(4.0%)		
	Total	176(88%)	24(12%)		
S7		Increase	Not Increase	.306>0.05	Not Sig.
	Urban	97(48.5%)	3(1.5%)		
	Rural	94(47.0%)	6(3.0%)		
	Total	191(95.5%)	9(4.5%)		
S8		Pay	Not Pay	0.508>0.05	Not Sig.
	Urban	26(13.0%)	74(37.0%)		
	Rural	22(11.0%)	78(39.0%)		
	Total	48(24%)	152(76.0%)		

S9		Effective	Not Effective	.028<0.05	Sig.
	Urban	71(35.5%)	29(14.5%)		
	Rural	84(42.0%)	16(8.0%)		
	Total	155(77.5%)	45(22.5%)		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire Dec. 2017)

Table 3 revealed that, according to residential area respondents are in favor of celebrity endorsement i.e. celebrity endorsement increase the level of awareness, helpful in recall, buy a brand when my favorite celebrity endorse it and its helpful in increasing the image and value of celebrity endorsed brand, Whereas, celebrity endorsement not helpful while I confused about selection of a two wheeler brand. But there is a significance difference among the respondents according to residential status that rural area respondents are more affected while selecting the two wheeler while evaluating the brand, more interested in celebrity endorsed brand & effective in making purchase decision as compare to urban area respondents at 95% level of significance.

Table 4: Consumer Perception about Celebrity Endorsement with Reference to Gender

Statement	Residential Status	Aware	Not Aware	Chi-Square Value/P Value	Result
S1	Male	92(46.0%)	8(4.0%)	.234>0.05	Not Sig.
	Female	96(48.0%)	4(2.0%)		
	Total	188(94.0%)	12(6.0%)		
S2		Affect	Not Effect	.050=0.05	
	Male	69(34.5%)	31(15.5%)		
	Female	81(40.5%)	19(9.5%)		
	Total	150(75.0%)	50(25.0%)		
S3		Recall	Not Recall	.016<0.05	Sig.
	Male	59(29.5%)	41(20.5%)		
	Female	75(37.5%)	25(12.5%)		
	Total	134(67.0%)	66(33.0%)		
S4		Believe	Not Believe	.031<0.05	Sig.
	Male	13(6.5%)	87(43.5%)		
	Female	25(12.5%)	75(37.5%)		
	Total	38(19.0%)	162(100.0%)		
S5		Interested	Not Interested	.008<0.05	Sig.
	Male	62(31.0%)	38(19.0%)		
	Female	79(39.5%)	21(10.5%)		
	Total	141(70.5%)	59(29.5%)		
S6		Buy	Not Buy	.384>0.05	Not Sig.
	Male	86(43.0%)	14(7.0%)		
	Female	90(45.0%)	10(5.0%)		
	Total	176(88%)	24(12.0%)		
S7		Increase	Not Increase	.306>0.05	Not Sig.
	Male	97(48.5%)	3(1.5%)		
	Female	94(47.0%)	6(3.0%)		
	Total	191(95.5%)	9(4.5%)		
S8		Pay	Not Pay	.508>0.05	Not Sig.
	Male	22(11.0%)	78(39.0%)		
	Female	26(13.0%)	74(37.0%)		
	Total	48(24.0%)	152(76.0%)		
S9		Effective	Not Effective	.028<0.05	Sig.
	Male	71(35.5%)	29(14.5%)		
	Female	84(42.0%)	16(8.0%)		
	Total	155(77.5%)	45(22.5%)		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire Dec. 2017)

Table 4 revealed that there is no significance difference among the respondents according to gender, they are in favor of that celebrity endorsement help to recall the two wheeler brand, interested in two wheeler brand which use used to celebrity endorsement and effective in making purchase decision, whereas, celebrity endorsement not helpful two remove confusion. But there is a significance difference among the respondents according to gender that female respondents are more in favor that celebrity endorsement increase awareness level, buy the celebrity endorsed brand and increase image and value of two wheeler product, whereas,

respondents are not in favor of pay high price of celebrity endorsed brand of two wheeler at 95% level of significance.

Table 5: Consumer Perception about Celebrity Endorsement with Reference to Age

Statement	Age	Aware	Not Aware	Chi-Square Value/P Value	Result
S1	18-25	60(30.0%)	4(2.0%)	.766>0.05	Not Sig.
	26-35	65(32.5%)	3(1.5%)		
	Above 35	63(31.5%)	5(2.5%)		
	Total	188(94.0%)	12(6.0%)		
S2		Affect	Not Effect	.347>0.05	Not Sig.
	18-25	52(26.0%)	12(6.0%)		
	26-35	50(25.0%)	18(9.0%)		
	Above 35	48(24.0%)	20(10.0%)		
	Total	150(75.0%)	50(25.0%)		
S3		Recall	Not Recall	.001<0.05	Sig.
	18-25	54(27.0%)	10(5.0%)		
	26-35	42(21.0%)	26(13.0%)		
	Above 35	38(19%)	30(15%)		
	Total	134(67%)	66(33%)		
S4		Believe	Not Believe	.003<0.05	Sig.
	18-25	21(10.5%)	43(21.5)		
	26-35	9(4.5%)	59(29.5%)		
	Above 35	8(4%)	60(30%)		
	Total	38(19%)	162(81%)		
S5		Interested	Not Interested	0.03<0.05	Sig.
	18-25	54(27%)	10(5%)		
	26-35	48(24%)	20(10%)		
	Above 35	39(19.5%)	29(14.5%)		
	Total	141(70.5%)	59(29.5%)		
S6		Buy	Not Buy	.067>0.05	Not Sig.
	18-25	61(30.5%)	3(1.5%)		
	26-35	56(28%)	12(6%)		
	Above 35	59(29.5%)	9(4.5%)		
	Total	176(88.0%)	24(12%)		
S7		Increase	Not Increase	.301>0.05	Not Sig.
	18-25	59(29.5%)	5(2.5%)		
	26-35	66(33%)	2(1%)		
	Above 35	66(33%)	2(1%)		
	Total	191(95.5%)	9(4.5%)		
S8		Pay	Not Pay	.000<0.05	Sig.
	18-25	27(13.5%)	37(18.5%)		
	26-35	15(7.5%)	53(26.5%)		
	Above 35	6(3%)	62(31%)		
	Total	48(24%)	152(76%)		
S9		Effective	Not Effective	.002<0.05	Sig.
	18-25	58(29%)	6(3%)		
	26-35	53(26.5)	15(7.5%)		
	Above 35	44(22%)	24(12%)		
	Total	155(77.5%)	45(22.5%)		

(Source: Primary data collected through questionnaire Dec. 2017)

Table 5 revealed that there is no significance difference among the respondents according to different age group that celebrity endorsement increase the level of awareness, affect the evaluation process, buy the celebrity endorsed brand and increase the image and value of celebrity endorsed two wheeler product. But there is a significance difference among the respondents according to different age group that celebrity endorsement help to recall the brand, interested to purchase celebrity endorsed brand and very effective in making purchase decision of two wheeler, whereas, not helpful to remove confusion and not in favor of pay high price of two wheeler endorsed by celebrity wheeler at 95% level of significance.

Conclusion:

Television and internet are most popular medium of celebrity endorsement and radio & magazine are least popular for celebrity endorsement. According to age and gender celebrity and non celebrity endorsement are equally popular but in case of residential area, rural area respondents are in favor of celebrity endorsement. Almost all the respondents irrespective of age, gender & residential status that they are in favor of, that celebrity endorsement increase awareness level, effect evaluation process, helpful in recall brand, interested to purchase celebrity endorsed brand, increase image & value of product/brand, and very effective in making purchase decision. But almost all respondents are not willing to pay high price of a two wheeler brand which is endorsed by celebrity and celebrity endorsement also not able to remove the confusion of the respondents. In the light of above discussion celebrity endorsement enhance awareness among customer and affect their selection process so marketers must carefully select the celebrities that are helpful in influencing the target customers positively. Marketers must choose celebrities according to important attributes required to influence the target population. When customer are confused about two wheeler they not believe only on celebrity endorser, they also considered other factors like mileage, price, resell value etc. Therefore, marketers should also highlight these features in celebrity endorsed advertisement.

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